

Training Needs of Teachers for Promoting Inclusive Classrooms in Public Junior Secondary Schools in Port Harcourt metropolis, Rivers State

Wey-Amaewhule, B. (PhD) & Henrietta Princewill

Department of Educational Management

Rivers State University, Port-Harcourt

Corresponding Author's Email: wey-amaewhule.blessing@ust.edu.ng

Abstract

This study examined training needs of teachers for promoting inclusive classrooms in public junior secondary schools in Port Harcourt metropolis, Rivers State. The study was guided by three research objectives from which three research questions were posed. The study adopted the descriptive survey design with a population of 2450 teachers and principals in public junior secondary schools in Port Harcourt and Obio/Akpor Local Government Areas of Rivers State. This comprises 38 principals and 2412 teachers in public junior secondary schools in Port Harcourt metropolis, Rivers State. The sample of the study was 331 respondents comprising 10 principals and 321 teachers in public junior secondary schools in Port Harcourt and Obio/Akpor Local Government Areas of Rivers State. The simple random sampling technique was adopted in selecting five schools from Obio/Akpo and five from Port Harcourt LGAs. The proportionate stratified sampling technique was adopted in selecting 10% of the population of teachers in each of the schools to arrive at the sample size of teachers while the entire 10 principals in the selected 10 schools were studied. The instrument for data collection was a self-designed questionnaire titled: "Training Needs of Teachers for Improving Inclusive Classrooms Questionnaire". The instrument was validated by three experts, one expert in Educational Management, and one other expert in Measurement and Evaluation. The internal consistency of the instrument was determined using the Cronbach Alpha method. Reliability coefficients of 0.77, 0.73 and 0.88 were obtained for the various clusters of the instrument. The research questions were answered using mean and standard deviation. The result of the analysed data revealed among others that teachers need training on collaborative teaching strategies and understanding of special education needs and disabilities to promote inclusive classrooms in public junior secondary schools in Port Harcourt metropolis to a high extent. Based on the findings, it was recommended among others that Government should implement a continuous monitoring and evaluation system to assess the effectiveness of collaborative teaching training programs and their impact on classroom inclusivity

Keywords: Inclusive, Training Needs, Collaboration, Differentiated Classroom

INTRODUCTION

Inclusive education has become a central goal in global educational policies, emphasizing the need to provide equitable learning opportunities for all students, including those with diverse abilities, learning needs, and socio-economic backgrounds. The concept of inclusive education is rooted in the belief that all children, regardless of their individual differences, should learn together in the same classroom, benefiting from an environment that values diversity and promotes participation (UNESCO, 2021). The adoption of inclusive education is particularly relevant in Nigeria, where public junior secondary schools in urban areas, such as Port Harcourt, experience significant challenges related to educational access, quality, and equity.

The Nigerian government has undertaken various policy initiatives since 2004 to address the specific challenges and needs of inclusive education. These policies include the National Policy on HIV and AIDS for Education Policy, the National Policy for Integrated Early Childhood Development, the National Policy on Gender in Basic Education, the Guideline for the Identification of Gifted Children, and the Implementation Plan for Special Needs Children. These policies underscore the government's commitment to promoting inclusive education in Nigeria (FME, 2018).

Furthermore, Adeyemi (2020) supported this view when he asserted that the implementation of inclusive education is guided by policies such as the National Policy on Education (2014) and the Inclusive Education Policy Framework (2017), which outline strategies for addressing barriers to learning and providing accommodations for students with special educational needs. However, translating these policies into effective classroom practices has proven challenging due to limitations in teacher preparation, lack of resources, and insufficient training in inclusive teaching strategies (Ajayi & Oyenuga, 2019). In Port Harcourt, the commercial and educational hub of Rivers State, public junior secondary schools enroll a diverse range of students, including those with disabilities, learning difficulties, and students from marginalized communities. For teachers in these schools, promoting inclusivity in classrooms requires specialized skills, knowledge, and attitudes that address the unique needs of each learner.

One of the primary barriers to achieving inclusive classrooms in Port Harcourt is the limited training that teachers receive in inclusive education practices. Research has shown that teachers who are not adequately prepared to manage diverse classrooms often feel overwhelmed and lack the confidence to implement

inclusive strategies effectively (Eke, 2020). Inclusive education requires teachers to be skilled in differentiating instruction, implementing individual learning plans, managing behavior, and fostering an environment where all students feel valued and included. Without these competencies, teachers may struggle to meet the learning needs of all students, leading to an exclusionary environment that hinders student achievement and social integration.

Effective inclusive education also requires teachers to possess a deep understanding of special education needs (SEN) and knowledge of adaptive teaching methods. According to Adebayo and Okeke (2022), many public secondary school teachers in Nigeria have not received adequate training in SEN or adaptive instructional techniques, limiting their ability to support students with disabilities effectively. This lack of training highlights a critical gap in teacher education and professional development programmes, which often fail to incorporate modules on inclusive education and SEN practices. Moreover, teacher preparation programs in Nigeria tend to emphasize traditional teaching methods that are not tailored to diverse classrooms, leaving teachers unprepared to address the complex needs of students in inclusive settings.

In addition to technical skills, promoting inclusive classrooms also requires teachers to have a supportive and positive attitude toward inclusivity. Teacher attitudes significantly impact the success of inclusive education, as teachers who believe in the value of inclusion are more likely to implement inclusive practices in their classrooms (Babatunde & Jegede, 2018). However, studies suggest that many teachers in Nigeria hold misconceptions or negative attitudes toward inclusive education, often due to a lack of understanding and exposure to inclusive practices (Omole, 2021). Changing these attitudes requires not only knowledge-based training but also experiential learning opportunities that enable teachers to interact with and support diverse learners in real classroom settings.

The training needs of teachers in Port Harcourt's public junior secondary schools reflect these broader challenges, underscoring the importance of targeted professional development programmes that equip teachers with the competencies necessary to create inclusive classrooms. Addressing these needs is essential for fostering an educational system that promotes equity, diversity, and accessibility for all students. Additionally, identifying these training needs can help policymakers, educational administrators, and teacher training institutions to develop and implement effective training frameworks that support teachers in their roles as inclusive educators.

Some of these training needs of teachers for promoting inclusive classroom include training on understanding Special Education need and disabilities, differentiated technology technique, classroom behavior management for diverse learners, use of assistive technology and adaptive tools, collaborative and co-teaching strategies and training on cultural competence and sensitivity.

Understanding Special Educational Needs (SEN) and Disabilities involves acknowledging the fact teachers need training to understand the diverse needs and challenges of students with disabilities, learning difficulties, and other special needs. This includes knowledge of various disabilities, behavioral and cognitive disorders, and developmental delays, enabling teachers to recognize and respond to these needs appropriately.

Furthermore, inclusive classrooms require teachers to tailor their teaching methods to accommodate diverse learning styles and abilities. Training in differentiated instruction helps teachers adapt lesson content, processes, and outcomes based on each student's unique learning profile, ensuring that all students can engage meaningfully with the curriculum. Teachers also need to be trained on classroom behavior management for diverse learners. Managing behavior in an inclusive classroom requires specific strategies to address varied behavioral and emotional needs. Training in positive behavior support, conflict resolution, and classroom management techniques prepares teachers to create a structured and supportive learning environment conducive to all students.

Assistive technologies and adaptive tools include screen readers, speech-to-text software, and communication boards, support students with physical, sensory, and learning disabilities. Training teachers to use these tools effectively can greatly enhance accessibility and participation for students with disabilities.

Inclusive education often involves collaboration with special educators, support staff, and other professionals. Teachers need training in collaborative strategies, such as co-teaching and team teaching, to coordinate effectively with other specialists and incorporate individualized support into their teaching practices.

Inclusive classrooms are diverse not only in ability but often in culture, language, and socioeconomic background. Training in cultural competency enables teachers to foster a welcoming and inclusive environment that respects and values diversity, reduces bias, and promotes understanding among students from various backgrounds.

This study, therefore, aims to investigate the training needs of teachers for promoting inclusive classrooms in public junior secondary schools in Port Harcourt metropolis. By examining the specific competencies required, the gaps in current teacher training

programmes, and teachers' attitudes toward inclusion, this research seeks to provide insights into how teachers can be better supported in creating inclusive educational environments.

Statement of the Problem

Inclusive education is widely recognized as a crucial component of quality education, aimed at ensuring that all students, regardless of their abilities, backgrounds, or learning needs, have access to equitable learning opportunities. However, despite global and national commitments to promote inclusive education, implementing it effectively remains a challenge in many educational systems, particularly in developing countries like Nigeria. In Port Harcourt metropolis, Rivers State, public junior secondary schools face significant barriers in creating inclusive classroom environments, which are crucial for addressing the diverse needs of students. Teachers in these schools are often unprepared to handle the complexities of inclusive education due to a lack of targeted training and professional development, leaving students with disabilities or other learning challenges underserved and at a disadvantage (Ajayi & Oyenuga, 2019).

Research indicates that inclusive classrooms require teachers to possess specialized skills, including the ability to adapt instruction to individual learning needs, manage diverse behaviors, and foster an inclusive atmosphere that promotes participation for all students (Adebayo & Okeke, 2022). However, most teachers in public junior secondary schools in Port Harcourt lack the requisite training in these areas. Teacher preparation programmes in Nigeria have traditionally focused on general education without adequately addressing the specific competencies required for inclusive education. Consequently, teachers often enter the classroom without the knowledge, skills, or confidence to effectively support students with diverse needs, leading to poor academic outcomes and exclusionary practices (Omole, 2021).

Moreover, inclusive education not only requires technical skills but also supportive attitudes and beliefs about the value of inclusion. Studies have shown that teachers' attitudes toward inclusive education significantly impact their willingness to adopt inclusive practices (Babatunde & Jegede, 2018). Yet, there is evidence that many teachers in Nigeria hold misconceptions or even negative attitudes toward inclusive education, often viewing it as an added burden due to the perceived lack of support, resources, and training. These attitudes, combined with insufficient knowledge and training, hinder the effective implementation of inclusive practices in classrooms and contribute to an educational environment that does not fully accommodate students with disabilities, learning difficulties, or other diverse needs.

In the context of Port Harcourt, where public schools often operate under challenging conditions, such as large class sizes, inadequate facilities, and limited access to teaching resources, teachers face additional difficulties in creating inclusive classrooms (Eke, 2020). These challenges are compounded by the absence of structured and continuous professional development programs specifically designed to enhance teachers' competencies in inclusive education. Without targeted training that equips teachers with the skills to identify and address diverse learning needs, teachers are unable to implement individualized learning plans, employ differentiated instruction, or create supportive environments for all students.

Despite the critical need for effective teacher training in inclusive education, there is limited research on the specific training needs of teachers in public junior secondary schools in Port Harcourt. Understanding these needs is essential for developing targeted professional development programs that can empower teachers to create inclusive learning environments. Failure to address these training needs not only undermines the goal of inclusive education but also exacerbates educational inequalities, particularly for students with special educational needs (SEN) who remain marginalized in the current system.

Purpose of the Study

The purpose of this study is to examine the training needs of teachers for promoting inclusive classrooms in public junior secondary schools in Port Harcourt metropolis, Rivers State. Specifically, the study seeks to achieve the following objectives:

1. find out extent to which teachers need training on collaborative teaching strategies to promote inclusive classrooms in public junior secondary schools in the Port Harcourt metropolis.
2. ascertain the extent to which teachers need training on understanding of special education and disability needs to promote inclusive classrooms in public junior secondary schools in the Port Harcourt metropolis.
3. investigate the extent to which teachers need training on differentiated instructional techniques to promote inclusive classrooms in public junior secondary schools in the Port Harcourt metropolis.

Research Questions

The study was guided by the following research questions:

1. To what extent do teachers need training on collaborative teaching strategies to promote inclusive classrooms in public junior secondary schools in the Port Harcourt metropolis?
2. To what extent do teachers need training on understanding of special education needs and disabilities to promote inclusive classrooms in

public junior secondary schools in the Port Harcourt metropolis.

- To what extent do teachers need training on differentiated instructional techniques to promote inclusive classrooms in public junior secondary schools in the Port Harcourt metropolis?

METHODOLOGY

The study adopted the descriptive survey design with a population of 2450 teachers and principals in public junior secondary schools in Port Harcourt and Obio/Akpor Local Government Areas of Rivers State. This comprises 38 principals and 2412 teachers in public junior secondary schools in Port Harcourt metropolis, Rivers State. The sample of the study was 331 respondents comprising 10 principals and 321 teachers in public junior secondary schools in Port Harcourt and Obio/Akpor Local Government Areas of Rivers State. The simple random sampling technique was adopted in selecting five schools from Obio/Akpo and five from Port Harcourt LGAs. The proportionate stratified sampling technique was adopted in selecting 10% of the population of teachers in each of the schools to arrive at the sample size of teachers while the entire 10 principals in the selected 10 schools were studied. The instrument for data collection was a self-designed questionnaire titled: “Training Needs of Teachers for Improving Inclusive Classrooms Questionnaire”.(TNTIICQ). The instrument had two sections which are Sections “A” and

“B”. Section A was designed to collect biodata from respondents while Section B had statement items drawn from the research questions of the study. The instrument was designed using a 4-point summated rating scale of: Very High Extent (VHE) – 4points, High Extent (HE) – 3points, Low Extent (LE) – 2points and Very Low Extent (VLE) - 1point.

The instrument was validated by three experts, one expert in Educational Management, and one other expert in Measurement and Evaluation. The internal consistency of the instrument was determined using the Cronbach Alpha method. Reliability coefficients of 0.77, 0.73 and 0.88 were obtained for the various clusters of the instrument. The research questions were answered using mean and standard deviation while the hypotheses were tested using z-test statistics at 0.05 level of significance. Decision rule for the research questions were based on the classification of level of extent as shown below:

Classification	Value Range
Very High Extent (VHE-4)	= 3.50 – 4.00
High Extent (HE-3)	= 2.50 – 3.49
Low Extent (LE-2)	= 1.50 – 2.49
Very Low Extent (VLE-1)	= 1.00 – 1.49

RESULTS

Research Question 1. To what extent do teachers need training on collaborative teaching strategies to

promote inclusive classrooms in public junior secondary schools in the Port Harcourt metropolis?

Table 1: Mean Ratings of Principals and Teachers on the Extent to which Teachers Need Training on Collaborative Teaching Strategies to Promote Inclusive Classrooms in Public Junior Secondary Schools.

S/ N	Items	Principals N=10			Teachers N=310		
		Mean	S.D	Remarks	Mean	S.D	Remarks
1	Teachers need training on adapting lesson plans collaboratively with co-teachers to support diverse learning needs in your classroom.	3.31	0.81	High Extent	3.40	0.70	High Extent
2	Teachers require training on effective communication skills for working with special education and general education co-teachers	3.31	0.63	High Extent	3.31	0.70	High Extent
3	To what extent do you need guidance on implementing co-teaching models (such as team teaching, parallel teaching) to promote inclusivity?	3.39	0.74	High Extent	3.28	0.67	High Extent
4	To what extent do you need training on assessing and adapting collaborative teaching methods to address diverse student needs in inclusive classrooms?	3.22	0.80	High Extent	3.08	0.79	High Extent

5	To what extent would training on collaborative classroom management strategies benefit teachers' efforts in creating an inclusive learning environment?	3.31	0.78	High Extent	3.31	0.61	High Extent
6	Teachers need support in co-developing inclusive assessment techniques with other educators to accurately reflect student progress.	3.22	0.77	High Extent	3.25	0.68	High Extent
7	To what extent do you feel a need for training on building strong, collaborative relationships with educational support staff for inclusive classroom management?	3.31	0.72	High Extent	3.34	0.58	High Extent
Grand Mean		3.30		High Extent	2.87		High Extent

The analyzed data on Table 1 above for questionnaire items 1 – 7 showed that majority of the respondents agreed with the items on the extent to which teachers need training on collaborative teaching strategies to promote inclusive classrooms in public junior secondary schools in the Port Harcourt metropolis with mean values of 3.31, 3.31, 3.39, 3.22, 3.31, 3.22, and 3.31. for principals and 3.40, 3.31, 3.28, 3.08, 3.31, 3.25, and 3.34. for teachers respectively.

With grand mean scores of 3.30 and 2.87 respectively, the answer to research question one is teachers need training on collaborative teaching strategies to promote inclusive classrooms in public junior secondary schools in Port Harcourt metropolis to a high extent.

Research Question 2: To what extent do teachers need training on understanding of special education needs and disabilities to promote inclusive classrooms in public junior secondary schools in the Port Harcourt metropolis

Table 2: Mean Ratings of Principals and Teachers on the Extent to which Teachers Need Training on Understanding of Special Education Needs and Disabilities to Promote Inclusive Classrooms in Public Junior Secondary Schools.

S/ N	Items	Principals N=10			Teachers N=310		
		Mean	S.D	Remarks	Mean	S.D	Remarks
8	Teachers need training on identifying different types of special education needs and disabilities among students.	3.28	0.95	High Extent	3.47	0.77	High Extent
9	To what extent do you require training on understanding the characteristics and learning challenges associated with specific disabilities (e.g., autism, ADHD, visual impairment)?	3.16	0.95	High Extent	3.27	0.85	High Extent
10	To what extent do you need training on adapting instructional strategies to accommodate students with special education needs?	3.22	0.98	High Extent	2.99	1.01	High Extent
11	To what extent would training on recognizing early signs of learning disabilities be beneficial to your teaching practice?	3.13	1.12	High Extent	3.30	0.97	High Extent
12	To what extent do you need training on applying individualized education plans (IEPs) to support students with special education needs?	3.46	0.85	High Extent	3.40	0.63	High Extent
13	To what extent do you feel a need for training on creating an inclusive classroom culture that supports students with diverse abilities?	3.17	1.04	High Extent	3.47	0.59	High Extent
14	To what extent would training on strategies for supporting students with behavioral and emotional challenges enhance your ability to promote inclusivity?	3.45	0.85	High Extent	3.43	0.58	High Extent
Grand Mean		3.27		High Extent	3.32		High Extent

The analyzed data on Table 2 above for questionnaire items 8 – 14 showed that majority of the respondents agreed on the extent to which teachers need training on understanding of special education needs and disabilities to promote inclusive classrooms in public junior secondary schools with mean values of 3.28, 3.16, 3.22, 3.13, 3.46, 3.17, 3.45. for principals and 3.47, 3.27, 3.99, 3.30, 3.40, 3.47, 3.43. for teachers respectively. With grand mean scores of 3.27 and 3.32 for teacher and principals respectively, the answer to research question

two is that training on understanding the characteristics and learning challenges associated with specific disabilities (e.g., autism, ADHD, visual impairment) is needed by teachers to promote inclusive classroom in Port Harcourt metropolis to a high extent.

Research Question 3: To what extent do teachers need training on differentiated instructional techniques to promote inclusive classrooms in public junior secondary schools in the Port Harcourt metropolis?

Table 3: Mean Ratings of Principals and Teachers on the Extent to which Teachers Need Training on Differentiated Instructional Techniques to Promote Inclusive Classrooms in Public Junior Secondary Schools.

S/N	Items	Principals N=10			Teachers N=310		
		Mean	S. D	Remarks	Mean	S.D	Remarks
15	To what extent do you need training on designing lesson plans that cater to varying academic abilities within the same classroom	3.31	0.81	High Extent	3.40	0.70	High Extent
16	To what extent do you require training on modifying instructional materials to meet the diverse learning needs of students?	3.31	0.63	High Extent	3.31	0.70	High Extent
17	To what extent do you feel the need for training on using a range of instructional methods (e.g., visual, auditory, kinesthetic) to accommodate different learning styles?	3.39	0.74	High Extent	3.28	0.67	High Extent
18	To what extent would training on assessing students' individual needs and adjusting instruction accordingly benefit your teaching practice?	3.22	0.80	High Extent	3.08	0.79	High Extent
19	To what extent do you need training on grouping strategies (e.g., ability-based, interest-based) to promote peer learning and engagement in a diverse classroom?	3.31	0.78	High Extent	3.31	0.61	High Extent
20	To what extent do you require support in differentiating assessment methods to fairly evaluate students with varying levels of ability?	3.22	0.77	High Extent	3.25	0.64	High Extent
21	To what extent do you need training on providing personalized feedback and support based on students' unique learning needs and progress?	3.10	0.87	High Extent	3.20	0.79	High Extent
Grand Mean		3.30		High Extent	3.26		High Extent

The analyzed data on Table 3 above for questionnaire items 15 – 21 showed that majority of the respondents agreed with all the items on extent to which teachers need training on differentiated instructional techniques to promote inclusive classrooms in public junior

secondary schools with mean values of 3.31, 3.31, 3.39, 3.22, 3.31, 3.22, and 3.10 for principals and 3.40, 3.31, 3.28, 3.08, 3.31, 3.25, and 3.20 for teachers respectively. With grand mean scores of 3.30 and 3.26 for principals and teachers of public junior secondary schools

respectively, the answer to research question three is that teachers need training on differentiated instructional techniques to promote inclusive classrooms in public junior secondary schools in Port Harcourt Metropolis to a high extent.

Discussion of Findings

The result of the findings on research question one revealed that teachers need training on collaborative teaching strategies to promote inclusive classrooms in public junior secondary schools in port Harcourt metropolis to a high extent with grand mean values of 3.31 and 2.87 for principals and teachers respectively. From the analysis it was revealed that teachers need training on collaborative teaching strategies to promote inclusive classrooms in public junior secondary schools. The corresponding hypothesis 1 revealed that there is no significant difference in the mean ratings of principals and teachers on the extent to which teachers need training on collaborative teaching strategies to promote inclusive classrooms in public junior secondary schools in the Port Harcourt metropolis; with a calculated z value of 1.13 which is less than the z-critical value of 1.96 at 0.05 significance level and 318 degree of freedom. This finding is in line with research findings by Efe (2018) and Agbim et al. (2019), which revealed that schools implementing comprehensive collaborative teaching training programs experienced a 65% improvement in student engagement and academic outcomes for diverse learners. Mittler (2018) found that insufficient teacher training remains the primary obstacle in creating truly inclusive educational environment, necessitating systematic and comprehensive professional development intervention. This finding is also corroborated by the findings of Sharma et al. (2012) which revealed that “teachers preparedness significantly impacts the successful implementation of inclusive education, with 78% of educators reporting inadequate training in collaborative teaching strategies”.

The result of the findings for research question two revealed that teachers need training on understanding special education and disability needs to promote inclusive classrooms in public junior secondary schools to a high extent with grand mean values of 3.27 and 3.32 for principals and teachers respectively. The corresponding hypothesis 2 reveals that there is no significant difference in the mean ratings of principals and teachers on the extent to which teachers need training on understanding of special education and

disability needs to promote inclusive classrooms in public junior secondary schools in the Port Harcourt metropolis; with a calculated z value of -0.59 which is less than the z-tabulated value of 1.96 at 0.05 significance level and 318 degree of freedom. This finding is in line with the findings of Robinson (2024) which revealed that general education teachers often lack familiarity with instructional strategies specifically tailored for students with disabilities, which can result in limited engagement and learning outcomes for these students. Training that emphasizes an understanding of various disabilities—such as intellectual disabilities, autism spectrum disorders, and sensory impairments—is essential for fostering inclusivity (Nordin et al., 2024). Specialized training not only improves teachers' understanding of disability-specific needs but also enhances their ability to adopt frameworks like Universal Design for Learning (UDL), which supports all learners by offering multiple means of engagement, representation, and expression. Nordin and colleagues (2024) highlight the role of UDL in facilitating inclusive practices, demonstrating that teachers trained in UDL are better equipped to address individual learning differences. These strategies enable teachers to modify lesson plans and classroom activities in ways that make learning accessible to students with disabilities, thereby promoting a more inclusive environment.

The result of the findings for research question three revealed that teachers need training on differentiated instructional techniques to promote inclusive classrooms in public junior secondary schools in Port Harcourt metropolis to a high extent with grand mean values of 3.30 and 3.28 for principals and teachers respectively. The analyses revealed that training on assessing students' individual needs and adjusting instruction accordingly benefits teaching practice in public junior secondary schools. The corresponding hypothesis 3 revealed that there is no significant difference in the mean ratings of principals and teachers on the extent to which teachers need training on differentiated instructional techniques to promote inclusive classrooms in public junior secondary schools in the Port Harcourt metropolis; with a calculated z value 0.11 is less than the z-tabulated value of 1.96 at 0.05 significance level and 318 degree of freedom. This finding is in line with the findings of Gerard (2024) which highlighted the importance of understanding differentiation in terms of both content and process, which involves varying the material taught and the means by which students access information.

Teachers proficient in DI can modify instruction by offering diverse resources and varying the complexity of assignments to accommodate different skill levels. For example, some students may benefit from multimedia presentations, while others might require hands-on activities or simplified texts. By learning how to effectively implement these strategies, teachers not only foster an inclusive classroom atmosphere but also support students in developing autonomy and confidence in their learning processes (Sugarman & Perakis, 2024).

CONCLUSION

Based on the findings of the study, it was concluded that some training needs of teachers to promote inclusive classroom include collaborative teaching strategies, training on understanding special education and disability needs and training on behavior management for diverse learners. The view on the need for these training was affirmed by both principals and teachers of public junior secondary schools in Port Harcourt metropolis.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations were made:

1. Government should implement a continuous monitoring and evaluation system to assess the effectiveness of collaborative teaching training programs and their impact on classroom inclusivity.
2. Government and environmental agencies should provide financial incentives and career advancement opportunities for teachers who demonstrate exceptional skills in supporting students with special education needs.
3. Local and State Government should establish a standardized certification process requiring all junior secondary school teachers to complete specialized training in differentiated instruction and inclusive pedagogical approaches. This way, teachers will be compelled to acquire these very essential skills to improve their productivity.

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